

Научни допринос руководиоца Миодрага Михаљевића пројекту
174008

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PROJECT 174008

Project title:

Advanced Techniques of Cryptology, Image Processing and Computational Topology for Information Security

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	Бр. радова	Бр. поена на основу: PRAVILNIKA O POSTUPKU, NAČINU VREDNOVANJA I KVANTITATIVNOM ISKAZIVANJUNAУČNOISTRAŽIVAČКИH REZULTATA ISTRAŽIVAČA ("Sl. glasnik RS", br. 24/2016, 21/2017 i 38/2017)	Бр. Година на пројекту
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